

PLURIDENTITIES

WORKING PAPER 13

Work Package 5

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Problem statement

The rapid evolution of digital technologies continues to transform educational practices across Europe and the wider global context, reshaping how learners interact with languages in both formal and informal settings. Mobile applications, online platforms, AI-driven tools, and social media have become deeply intertwined with students' daily communicative repertoires, enabling new forms of linguistic engagement and creating opportunities for personalised, multimodal, and autonomous learning (Casanova et al., 2020; Yang & Baldwin, 2020). In this shifting landscape, technology mediates not only access to linguistic resources but also the construction of linguistic identities, as learners navigate multilingual online environments and participate in culturally diverse digital communities (Kamalova et al., 2020; Minei et al., 2021).

These developments have significant implications for multilingual and plurilingual education in contexts where linguistic diversity is shaped by a combination of historical, sociopolitical, and demographic factors. Spain, Belgium, the Netherlands, Aruba, and Sweden each present distinct sociolinguistic ecologies. Belgium and the Netherlands have established policies that protect certain regional languages and mandate foreign language education (Extra & Gorter, 2008), while Spain's linguistic landscape is characterised by regional bilingualism and historically rooted minority languages (Cenoz & Gorter, 2011; Vila et al., 2017). Aruba's postcolonial context reflects layered linguistic profiles tied to identity, migration, and education (Kester & Buijink, 2023), and Sweden's linguistic diversity has expanded due to sustained immigration (Oral & Lund, 2022). Despite these differences, learners across all five contexts are increasingly exposed to multilingual digital spaces that influence how they use, value, and identify with languages.

While the potential of technology to enhance multilingual practices is widely recognised (e.g., Maamuujav, 2025; Yu et al., 2024; Zhang-Wu, 2022), existing research also points to challenges concerning digital inequalities, varying teacher expertise, and the pedagogical integration of AI and other emerging tools (Huertas-Abril & Palacios-Hidalgo, 2025; Kaiser & Ivancheva, 2022). Not all students have equal access to devices or stable internet connections, nor are all languages equally represented in digital spaces. This dual inequality can shape students' experiences with language learning technologies and, consequently, their ability to develop linguistic capital. Moreover, although AI-driven tools such as chatbots can support learners' confidence and motivation through immediate feedback and simulated interaction (Huertas-Abril & Palacios-Hidalgo, 2023; Li, 2024), their uncritical use raises concerns regarding autonomy, critical thinking, and the balance between automated learning and human

interaction (Alvarez & Lane, 2023). In addition, the use of AI-driven technologies in educational contexts raises concerns related to data protection, privacy, and digital safety, which are particularly salient when working with minors and require careful pedagogical and institutional mediation (UNESCO, 2023).

Teachers play a crucial role in mediating these opportunities and challenges. Across educational systems. There is a growing expectation in some educational systems for educators to integrate digital tools to support translanguaging, promote engagement, and create inclusive multilingual learning environments (García & Wei, 2014; Mohd Tahir et al., 2018), although its adoption varies across settings. Yet research indicates that many teachers feel insufficiently prepared to implement technology-enhanced multilingual pedagogies or to leverage students' diverse linguistic repertoires, particularly when they do not share all of their students' languages (Cunliffe, 2019; Sierens & van Avermaet, 2014). Professional development initiatives, including emerging AI competency frameworks for teachers, attempt to address these gaps, but further empirical research is needed to understand how teachers in different contexts conceptualise and enact technology-mediated multilingual teaching.

The Pluridentities multidimensional framework offers a valuable conceptual lens for examining these issues. It proposes that plurilingual identity development is shaped by the interaction of linguistic capital, learning environments, technology, and language policy (Pluridentities, 2025). However, despite its relevance, there is limited cross-national empirical evidence demonstrating how these four components operate across different educational systems. Current research tends to focus on single-country studies, making it difficult to assess how sociocultural variables, policy differences, and historical language regimes influence students' and teachers' practices and perceptions. Moreover, empirical studies exploring how teachers' technology mediation strategies directly influence students' development of plurilingual identity and motivation are still limited. This working paper investigates this teacher-student dynamic within technology-mediated multilingual classrooms.

To address these gaps, a transnational comparative perspective is needed. The five contexts included in this working paper offer an opportunity to examine how students' attitudes towards languages, their use of technology, and their linguistic identity development intersect across diverse sociolinguistic environments. A quantitative comparison among secondary-education students in Spain, Belgium, the Netherlands, Aruba, and Sweden will enable the identification of shared trends and context-specific patterns. Meanwhile, a qualitative comparison involving

both students and teachers in Spain and the Netherlands will provide insight into how learners and educators navigate technological integration, engage with multilingual realities, and make sense of the ways technology-enhanced practices shape students' linguistic identity development.

Therefore, this working paper seeks to generate a nuanced and empirically grounded understanding of how technology, language learning, and identity interrelate across varied national settings. By integrating cross-national quantitative data in all the countries involved in the project with comparative qualitative context-specific perspectives (Spain and the Netherlands), the working paper aims to contribute to evidence-based strategies that foster inclusive, plurilingual, and digitally informed educational environments. Ultimately, this research responds to the urgent need to understand how digitalisation shapes language attitudes and identity formation in increasingly multilingual societies, and how educators can be supported in using technology to promote linguistic diversity and learner agency. Moreover, it intends to respond to the following research questions (RQs):

- Research question 1 (RQ1). What are the attitudes and practices of secondary-education students in Spain, Belgium, the Netherlands, Aruba, and Sweden regarding the use of technology (inside and outside the classroom) for language-related activities, and how do these relate to their linguistic attitudes and identity development?
- Research question 2 (RQ2). What are the attitudes and practices of secondary-education teachers in Spain, Belgium, the Netherlands, Aruba, and Sweden regarding the use of technology (inside and outside the classroom) for language-related activities, and how do these relate to students' linguistic attitudes and identity development?

Methodology

Research design

This working paper reports on a mixed-method research design that combines a cross-national quantitative component with a qualitative comparative component. It aims to examine how technology use intersects with linguistic attitudes and plurilingual identity development among students and teachers across diverse contexts. To achieve this, the design integrates an exploratory cross-sectional quantitative approach (Adèr & Mellenbergh, 1999) with qualitative thematic analysis.

The quantitative strand focuses on students enrolled in secondary education. The age ranges were as follows: 14–18 years in Spain and Belgium, 15–18 years in Sweden, and 16–18 years in the Netherlands and Aruba. A large-scale survey was developed to collect data on students' technology practices inside and outside the classroom, their attitudes towards languages, and indicators of linguistic identity development. This cross-national comparison enables the identification of shared tendencies and context-specific differences across varied educational systems and linguistic ecologies.

Complementing this, the qualitative strand centres on teachers in Spain and the Netherlands, enabling an in-depth exploration of how educators perceive and implement technology in relation to students' multilingual practices and identity formation. A phenomenological approach was adopted to capture the lived experiences and professional reflections of secondary education teachers. Data were gathered through individual semi-structured interviews with teachers in both countries. Additionally, focus group discussions with Spanish and Dutch students provide further insight into learners' perceptions, enabling the interpretation of the quantitative patterns through the lens of student and teacher experiences.

By combining breadth and depth, the mixed-method design allows for a holistic understanding of the interplay between technology, language attitudes, and identity formation. The quantitative data illuminate general patterns across five national contexts, while the qualitative findings contextualise these patterns within the perspectives and practices of educators and learners. Together, these complementary strands offer a robust and multidimensional account of how digital environments shape plurilingual experiences in contemporary secondary education.

Participants

Participants in the quantitative research

A non-probabilistic convenience sampling technique was employed for the selection of participants. Participant eligibility was determined primarily by their proximity to the researchers (i.e., schools with which the researchers had previously made contact), a criterion that ensured operational practicality and enabled the recruitment of individuals with immediate and relevant exposure to the central research context. The main limitation of this sampling technique—its non-representativeness and the potential for selection bias—is explicitly recognised. Consequently, the findings are not intended to be statistically generalisable but are instead valued for their ability to generate preliminary insights and thick, descriptive data within the defined study parameters.

On the one hand, the quantitative strand focuses on students enrolled in secondary education. The age ranges were as follows: 14+ years in Spain and Belgium, 15+ years in Sweden, and 16+ years in the Netherlands and Aruba. A total of 2817 students answered the survey: 45.0% considered themselves boys ($n = 1267$) and 53.0% identified as girls ($n = 1493$), 1.0% considered themselves X ($n = 28$), and 1.0% preferred not to respond ($n = 29$). The distribution of students per country is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1

Number of students participating in the survey per country

Note. Own elaboration.

On the other hand, 253 teachers answered the survey: 32.0% considered themselves men ($n = 81$), 66.8% identified as women ($n = 169$), 0.4% considered themselves X ($n = 1$), and 0.8% preferred not to respond ($n = 2$). Their average teaching experience was 14.06 years ($SD = 10.05$). The distribution of participating teachers per country is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2

Number of teachers participating in the survey per country

Note. Own elaboration.

Participants in the qualitative research

A combination of purposive and convenience sampling strategies was employed to recruit participants for the qualitative phase of the study in Spain and the Netherlands, the two contexts analysing the role of technology as part of the Pluridentities Work Package 5. Recruitment was built on the preceding survey phase, in which both teachers and students were invited to indicate whether they were willing to take part in a follow-up focus group or interview. Individuals who had expressed interest during the survey were contacted first, after which additional recruitment occurred through the same channels used previously.

In the Netherlands, secondary-education modern foreign language teachers working in regular Dutch schools were invited to participate in individual interviews. Initial recruitment targeted teachers who had completed the survey and had agreed to be approached for follow-up research. Additional teachers were subsequently recruited through the researcher's professional networks and subject-specific professional organisations, mirroring the convenience-based approach used in the survey. In selecting teachers, efforts were made to include representation of the modern foreign languages most commonly taught in Dutch secondary education (English, French, German, and Spanish). All participating teachers ($n = 37$) volunteered to take part. As with all convenience-based sampling, the resulting group reflects those teachers who were reachable through these networks and willing to participate. Moreover, student recruitment likewise began with those who had participated in the survey and indicated interest in joining a follow-up focus group. Their teachers, both survey participants and teachers newly recruited for the qualitative phase, distributed information about the focus groups within their upper-

secondary classes, allowing students to volunteer directly. Finally, 35 students took part in the focus groups. The student data were generated across seven focus groups, each comprising 3–7 participants and included students from five different secondary schools.

Similarly, in Spain initial recruitment targeted teachers who had completed the survey and had agreed to be approached for follow-up research, being both language and non-language teachers. After this, individual, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 16 secondary education teachers. An interview protocol had been previously developed in the framework of the Pluridentities project with open-ended questions focusing on their experiences regarding the use of technology to support students' linguistic diversity, attitudes and identity development. Interviews lasted approximately 60 minutes each and were audio-recorded. Moreover, six focus group discussions were facilitated with the 28 student participants, each comprising 4-6 participants. From the pool of volunteers, 28 students were randomly selected, ensuring each of them studied at a different school to guarantee school diversity. A specific discussion guide was used, prompting students to discuss their perspectives and attitudes towards different languages and how the usage of technology (both inside and outside the high school) is linked to their attitudes and identity development. Each focus group session lasted approximately 30 minutes and was audio-recorded. Finally, both interviews and focus groups were subsequently transcribed verbatim, and translated into English. Researchers acknowledge that translation from Spanish to English and from Dutch to English is an interpretive act. To mitigate bias, they collaboratively translated and verified key data excerpts, ensuring semantic and contextual accuracy was preserved during analysis.

Instruments and data collection

This mixed-method working paper draws on two data sources: (1) cross-national survey data from students and teachers in Spain, Belgium, the Netherlands, Aruba, and Sweden, and (2) qualitative data from interviews and focus groups conducted in Spain and the Netherlands.

For the quantitative part, two surveys, one for students and one for teachers, were constructed for the purposes of this study. Both surveys drew on items from several existing validated instruments, supplemented with additional researcher-developed questions to address study-specific aims. The selection and adaptation of items ensured both relevance to the research context and alignment with established measurement practices. Both surveys were developed by the Pluridentities consortium so as to gather information about: (1) students' background information, linguistic repertoire and language usage, sense of identification and belonging, school composition, attitudes towards multilingualism and multilingual practices at school,

language learning motivation and technology for language learning; and (2) teachers' background information, linguistic repertoire, sense of identification, multilingualism and language policy at school, multilingual practices, technological skillset, and use of technology to enhance language learning among students. Quantitative data were collected between April and October 2025. For this working paper, only items related to participants' background information and technology use are analysed. Items were formatted as multiple-choice questions, frequency selections (never–daily, including a “for a certain period” option), and five-point Likert scales (1 = strongly disagree; 5 = strongly agree). Reliability analyses showed satisfactory internal consistency for both instruments (students: $\alpha = 0.979$; teachers: $\alpha = 0.880$), following the recommendations from Taber (2018).

Qualitative data were collected between July and October 2025. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 37 secondary education teachers from both contexts and guided by an interview protocol developed within the Pluridentities project and adapted to local contexts by the researchers. Questions explored teachers' experiences using technology in general and also to support students' linguistic diversity, attitudes, and identity development. Each interview lasted approximately 60 minutes, was audio-recorded, transcribed verbatim, and translated into English. Additionally, six focus group discussions were held with 28 students using a structured discussion guide addressing their language attitudes and the role of technology inside and outside school. Sessions lasted around 30 minutes and were likewise recorded, transcribed, and translated.

Data collection for teachers and students was conducted separately to preserve the integrity of each perspective and avoid potential power dynamics influencing participants' responses.

This study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Vrije Universiteit Brussel (Ref. No. ECHW_593-WP4-5_Phase1), the Ethics Committee of the University of Amsterdam (Ref. No. FMG-13660), and by the Ethics Committee for Research Involving Humans (Comité Ético de Investigación con Humanos – CEIH) of the University of Córdoba (Ref. No. CEIH-25-28), and all participants provided informed consent prior to their involvement.

Data analysis

Quantitative and qualitative data were analysed separately but approached as complementary strands within the mixed-method design.

Quantitative analysis began with coding and entry of all survey responses into Microsoft Excel for initial cleaning and organisation, followed by transfer to SPSS Statistics (Version 29.0 for MacOS) for formal analysis. Descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) were used to summarise participants' characteristics and provide an initial picture of technology use before further interpretation.

Qualitative analysis followed Braun and Clarke's (2006, 2021) six-phase thematic analysis. First, the research team familiarised themselves with the interview and focus group transcripts through repeated readings. Second, initial codes were generated in Atlas.ti 25.0.1, with separate preliminary coding frameworks developed for teachers and students. Third, codes were clustered into potential themes, noting convergences and divergences across the two participant groups. Fourth, themes were reviewed, refined, and compared collaboratively to ensure internal coherence. Fifth, themes were defined and named, and a thematic network capturing their relationships was constructed. Finally, the themes were integrated into a coherent narrative for the working paper, supported by illustrative extracts from both datasets.

A reflexive stance was maintained throughout the qualitative analysis. Researchers acknowledged how their positionalities and intersecting identities could shape interpretation and therefore engaged in continuous dialogue to challenge assumptions. This reflexive practice, combined with deep and sustained immersion in the material—"living with the data" (Creswell & Creswell, 2017)—supported the development of nuanced and analytically robust themes.

Results

Results are presented in the following sections. Due to item-level missingness, analytic Ns vary per analysis; N is reported for each test.

Quantitative results: students' perspectives

Use of devices

This working paper examined whether the frequency of device use (e.g., smartphone, laptop, tablet, Chromebook) in class for class-related tasks differed across countries. Across the full student sample, device use was very common: only about 3.0% of students reported *never* using a device for school tasks, whereas about one third used a device *daily* and another roughly one quarter used it *multiple times a day* or *for specific periods*. However, this pattern varied significantly across countries. A Pearson chi-square test showed a significant association between country and device use, $\chi^2(24, N = 2,469) = 315.54, p < .001$. In Sweden and Spain, daily or more-than-daily use was most common, whereas in Belgium and the Netherlands a larger share of students reported *weekly* rather than (multiple) daily use. Aruba showed an intermediate pattern, with relatively high proportions of both daily and multiple-times-a-day use. These differences indicate that students' digital learning environments are not uniform across the participating countries. Overall, only about 4% of students report that their teacher never asks them to complete assignments on a computer at home or outside school. Around 10% experience this a few times a year, and 11% monthly. The majority say this is a regular expectation: roughly 29% report being asked to do this weekly, 24% daily, and 13% multiple times a day, with another 10% indicating this happens mainly for specific periods or projects.

Teachers asking for devices

Overall, only about 4% of students report that their teacher never asks them to complete assignments on a computer at home or outside school. Around 10% experience this a few times a year, and 11% monthly. The majority say this is a regular expectation: roughly 29% report being asked to do this weekly, 24% daily, and 13% multiple times a day, with another 10% indicating this happens mainly for specific periods or projects. The frequency with which teachers ask students to use a device differs significantly between countries, $\chi^2(24, N = 2,476) = 303.87, p < .001$, Cramer's $V = .18$. In Belgium and the Netherlands, relatively more students report that teachers ask for device use *daily* or *multiple times a day*. In Spain, device use is often *daily* but less often *multiple times a day*. In Aruba, requests are more concentrated in *specific periods* (e.g., projects), while Sweden shows a more moderate distribution across weekly and daily use.

Technology-supported multilingual learning attitudes

Technology-supported multilingual learning attitudes were assessed with a seven-item scale (Technology 2, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14). The items tap how students perceive technology (including AI tools, apps, games and social media) as a resource for learning and using multiple languages, for example: “Technology provides me with easy access to resources for learning multiple languages,” “Using technology (like apps, games, or AI tools) makes it easier to learn the languages taught at school,” and “Being multilingual makes me feel confident when using technology, social media, or AI tools.” Responses were given on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree). An exploratory factor analysis indicated a clear one-factor solution, and internal consistency was good (Cronbach’s $\alpha = 0.85$). A composite score was calculated as the mean of the seven items, such that higher scores reflect more positive attitudes towards using technology to support multilingual language learning and multilingual identities. In the total sample ($n = 2,533$; 284 missing), the mean score was 3.73 ($SD = 0.73$; median = 3.71), with the full response range being used (1–5), indicating overall rather positive technology-related attitudes among students.

Students in Spain reported the highest mean score ($M = 4.09$, $SD = 0.64$, $N = 829$), followed by Aruba ($M = 3.83$, $SD = 0.67$, $N = 171$). Belgium ($M = 3.55$, $SD = 0.67$, $N = 1,004$), Sweden ($M = 3.47$, $SD = 0.80$, $N = 334$) and the Netherlands ($M = 3.44$, $SD = 0.69$, $N = 195$) showed somewhat lower, but still clearly positive, average scores.

To explore whether the distribution of technology-supported multilingual learning attitudes differed by country, we cross-tabulated the scale with country. A Pearson chi-square test indicated a significant association between country and students’ technology attitudes, $\chi^2(156, N = 2,533) = 547.42$, $p < .001$. However, this analysis involved a large number of sparsely populated categories (57.5% of cells with expected counts < 5), because the scale is essentially continuous. The chi-square result should therefore be interpreted with caution, and the mean differences reported above provide a more interpretable summary of cross-country variation.

Multilingual digital practices

Multilingual digital practices were examined across the five countries using a one-way ANOVA with country as the grouping variable. This 4-item scale captures students’ multilingual digital practices, that is, the extent to which they use social media, AI tools and online communication in languages other than their home language. The scale showed acceptable internal consistency (Cronbach’s $\alpha = .69$), and students scored slightly above the midpoint of the 1–5 response scale (overall $M = 3.43$, $SD = 0.88$; $N = 2,533$), indicating moderately frequent use of digital

technologies in languages other than the home language. The ANOVA revealed a significant effect of country, $F(4, 2528) = 12.65, p < .001, \eta^2 \approx .02$, suggesting small but meaningful cross-country differences. Games–Howell post-hoc comparisons showed that students in Aruba reported significantly higher levels of multilingual digital practices than students in Spain, Belgium, and the Netherlands, while Swedish students also scored significantly higher than those in Spain. Differences between Belgium, the Netherlands and Sweden were relatively small and mostly non-significant. Overall, these findings indicate that the intensity of multilingual digital engagement varies across contexts, with Aruba and, to a lesser extent, Sweden standing out as the settings where students most frequently use digital technologies in languages other than their home language.

We used two distinct technology-related scales. The technology-supported multilingual learning attitudes scale (7 items; $\alpha = .85$) captures how positively students view technology as a resource for learning and using multiple languages (e.g., perceived usefulness, enjoyment, confidence). The multilingual digital practices scale (4 items; $\alpha = .69$) instead measures how frequently students actually use digital tools (social media, AI tools, online videos, chatting with friends) in languages other than their home language. Although both scales are moderately correlated conceptually, they tap different dimensions: evaluative beliefs versus everyday behaviour.

This distinction is clearly reflected in the country patterns. Spanish students report the most positive attitudes towards technology for multilingual learning (attitude scale: $M = 4.09$), yet they show the lowest level of multilingual digital practices (practice scale: $M = 3.30$), whereas students in Aruba and Sweden display comparatively higher behavioural engagement in using other languages online. This suggests an attitude–behaviour gap: Spanish students value technology as a tool for multilingual learning, but this does not consistently translate into frequent use of non-home languages in their digital lives. A plausible explanation is the strong online presence of Spanish as a global language, which reduces the necessity to switch to other languages, in contrast to more structurally multilingual contexts such as Aruba or settings where English dominates youth digital culture, such as Sweden.

the relationship between the two technology-related scales across countries was also examined. Descriptively, mean scores on both technology-supported multilingual learning attitudes and multilingual digital practices were above the midpoint of the 1–5 scales in all five contexts, indicating generally positive views of technology and a moderate degree of multilingual engagement online. Spanish students reported the highest mean level of technology-supported

multilingual learning attitudes ($M = 4.09$), followed by Aruba ($M = 3.83$). In contrast, multilingual digital practices were most frequent in Aruba ($M = 3.78$) and Sweden ($M = 3.53$), with Belgium and the Netherlands in the mid-range ($M_s \approx 3.43\text{--}3.44$) and Spain showing the lowest mean on this behavioural scale ($M = 3.30$).

Within each country, attitudes and practices were positively and significantly correlated. In Belgium, the Netherlands, Aruba and Sweden, the association between technology-supported multilingual learning attitudes and multilingual digital practices was moderate (Pearson's r ranging from .50 to .59, all $p < .001$), suggesting that students who feel more positive about technology as a tool for multilingual learning also tend to engage more frequently in multilingual online activities. In Spain, however, the correlation was noticeably weaker ($r = .37$, $p < .001$), indicating a looser link between evaluative beliefs and everyday behaviour. Taken together with the mean differences, this pattern points to an attitude–behaviour gap in the Spanish context: students express very positive views of technology for multilingual learning, but this does not translate to the same extent into frequent use of non-home languages in their digital practices.

Focusing on the Spanish subsample, it was examined whether *multilingual digital practices* varied as a function of students' self-reported language profile (monolingual, bilingual, plurilingual). Mean scores increased monotonically across the three groups: monolingual students reported the lowest level of multilingual digital practices ($M = 2.84$, $SD = 1.16$, $N = 84$), followed by bilingual students ($M = 3.24$, $SD = 1.00$, $N = 448$), with plurilingual students reporting the highest frequency of using other languages online ($M = 3.52$, $SD = 0.89$, $N = 293$). A one-way ANOVA showed a significant effect of language profile, $F(2, 822) = 17.64$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2 \approx .04$. Because the homogeneity of variances assumption was violated (Levene's test, $p = .001$), Games–Howell post-hoc tests were used. These revealed that plurilingual students scored significantly higher than both monolingual ($p < .001$) and bilingual students ($p < .001$), and bilingual students in turn scored significantly higher than monolinguals ($p = .011$). This pattern indicates that, within Spain, students who identify as plurilingual are substantially more likely to engage in multilingual digital practices than their monolingual and bilingual peers.

Quantitative results: teachers' perspectives

Teachers asking for devices

Across all countries ($n = 223$), teachers reported asking students to complete assignments on a computer at home or outside school fairly regularly. Only about 3% said they *never* do this.

Around 17–18% do so a few times a year, and about 17% once a month. The largest group, almost 30%, indicated that they ask for computer-based homework weekly, while a further 16% do so daily. About 8% reported asking for such assignments multiple times a day, and 9% said they use them only for specific periods (e.g., projects).

A chi-square test comparing the distribution across countries was marginal and not statistically significant ($\chi^2(24) = 36.06, p = .054$), so we interpret these results as describing a broadly similar pattern of computer-based homework use in all five contexts rather than meaningful cross-national differences.

Digital literacy self-efficacy

Teachers' perceived digital literacy was measured with four items adapted from the "My own technological skillset" section of the questionnaire. Respondents indicated how often each statement applied to them on a 5-point Likert frequency scale (1 = *never*, 2 = *rarely*, 3 = *sometimes*, 4 = *often*, 5 = *very often*). The items were:

1. *I know how to solve my own technical problems.*
2. *I can easily acquire (new) technological skills.*
3. *I keep up with important new technologies.*
4. *I have the skills I need to use technology.*

A principal component analysis supported a one-factor solution (eigenvalue = 3.07, 61.5% of variance explained; factor loadings = .72–.88). Internal consistency of the four-item scale was good (Cronbach's $\alpha = .88$). For each teacher we computed a mean score across the four items, so that higher values indicate higher perceived digital literacy self-efficacy.

Teachers' digital literacy self-efficacy is generally high, as shown in Figure 3. Scores cluster were between 3 and 5 on the 5-point scale, with a mean of 3.83 (SD = 0.76, N = 224). Very few teachers rate themselves at the very low end of the scale, indicating that most feel reasonably confident in their own digital skills.

Figure 3

Teachers' digital literacy self-efficacy

Note. Own elaboration.

Frequency of computer-based homework assignments

As shown in Figure 4, most teachers use computer-based homework regularly. About 30% ask for it weekly, and another 24% do so daily. Occasional use is also common. Roughly 17–18% assign it monthly and 17% only a few times a year. Very few never use it. Only about 3% of teachers say they never ask students to do homework on a computer; around 8–9% restrict it to specific periods or projects.

Figure 4

Frequency of computer-based homework assignments

Note. Own elaboration.

Most teachers use computer-based homework regularly. About 30% ask for it weekly, and another 24% do so daily. Occasional use is also common. Roughly 17–18% assign it monthly and 17% only a few times a year. Very few never use it. Only about 3% of teachers say they never ask students to do homework on a computer; around 8–9% restrict it to specific periods or projects.

Qualitative results: students' perspectives

This section provides a comparative analysis of students' perspectives on the use of technology (both inside and outside the classroom) for language-related activities in two distinct European contexts: Spain and the Netherlands.

Points of convergence

A comparative analysis of the teacher responses across both national contexts reveals four principal areas of convergence:

- Technology as a convenient and efficient tool for immediate needs. In both contexts, students value technology primarily for its practicality. Spanish students associate technology with promptness, usefulness, and specific linguistic support (i.e., pronunciation). Similarly, Dutch students describe technology as an everyday, utilitarian tool: translation apps, dictionaries, and platforms like Duolingo or DeepL are used to

solve immediate problems, check meaning, or clarify uncertain points. This utilitarian orientation positions technology as a fast, responsive companion rather than as a comprehensive learning pathway. In both countries students articulate a shared understanding: technology is helpful “in the moment,” but not necessarily transformative for deep learning.

- Preference for human mediation and social interaction. Despite recognizing technological advantages, students in both contexts express a strong preference for human-mediated learning. Spanish students clearly state that, for actual learning, they often prefer “traditional” teacher-led approaches. Similarly, Dutch students underline the motivational impact of face-to-face interaction and repeatedly describe social exchanges as the most powerful drivers of language learning and motivation for it. In both groups, interpersonal communication is positioned as the heart of meaningful language learning.
- Limited trust in translation and AI tools. A notable convergence is students’ distrust of automated assistance. Both Dutch and Spanish students perceive a “lack of reliability” and express concerns that technology may encourage complacency or “easing off”—doing less work themselves. Dutch students, meanwhile, explicitly note that apps like Duolingo or translation systems often fail in real communicative situations: being able to complete tasks within an app is not equivalent to real-life communicative ability.
- Recognition of out-of-class learning through media exposure. Both groups of participants report that out-of-class engagement with media—films, series, games, music, and social networks—contributes to language familiarity. Students in both countries perceive technology as extending language contact beyond the classroom, even if they do not view it as sufficient for mastering the language.

Key differences

Conversely, the analysis identified four principal points of divergence between the two contexts:

- Depth of reflection on competence and learning processes. Spanish students frame risks primarily in terms of complacency, limits, and unreliability, and their reflections focus on behavioural risks—doing less work, becoming dependent, or encountering incorrect information. Dutch students, however, articulate a more metacognitive understanding of competence: they describe a clear distinction between knowing how to complete app-based tasks and being able to communicate authentically. This insight suggests a deeper awareness of the difference between procedural success and communicative proficiency. Dutch students also explicitly note the tension between efficiency and genuine ability.

- Role of social interaction as a central motivational driver. While both groups acknowledge the importance of human interaction, Dutch students place greater emphasis on social motivation than their Spanish counterparts. They refer to specific multilingual family dynamics, holiday experiences, and social media interactions with relatives abroad, which reflects a more sustained engagement with real-life communicative opportunities.
- Classroom technology policies. Dutch students comment on how school policies shape their experiences, as they describe a landscape of school-level variation in laptop use, restrictions on phones (which is, in fact, a national ban in Dutch schools), and differences between subjects in how digital platforms are implemented. They discuss both advantages (e.g., engaging activities like Kahoot) and drawbacks (distraction, missing explanations, monotony in paper-only lessons). Spanish students do not emphasize policy variability, as there is a national law that prohibits the use of smartphones in class, so the use of classroom technologies (e.g., Chromebooks, tablets) depends mainly on the teacher.
- Use of plurilingual repertoires. Dutch students report a purpose-driven use of other languages, often their home languages, to support vocabulary recall or comprehension. Spanish students do not explicitly discuss the use of other known languages as learning tools. Their account focuses instead on preferences for teachers' mediation or traditional resources.

Qualitative results: teachers' perspectives

This section compares and contrasts findings from the data obtained through the semi-structured interviews on teachers' perspectives towards the use of technology (both inside and outside the classroom) for language-related activities in two contexts: the Netherlands and Spain.

Points of convergence

A comparative analysis of the teacher responses across both national contexts reveals three principal areas of convergence:

- Technology as motivating and access-enhancing. Participants from both contexts describe technology as a motivational catalyst that can make language tasks more engaging and accessible. In the Spanish sample, "increase in learner motivation" emerges as the most frequent advantage, closely followed by accessibility and adaptability. Dutch teachers similarly emphasize that digital tools can render tasks more engaging and easier and faster lesson preparation (although technology can actually slow down the lesson and takes a lot of preparation when the students need to be the

ones using digital tools for the lesson), which, in turn, supports learners' sense of competence and facilitates differentiated instruction. Across settings, teachers perceive that multimodal resources, creative online tasks, and flexible digital materials can cater to varied proficiency levels and learning preferences, thereby broadening participation.

- Importance of digital literacy and deconstruction of the concept of the “digital native.” A strong parallel concerns scepticism about students' perceived digital competence. Spanish teachers explicitly identify a lack of critical thinking as the predominant risk, and they also highlight recurrent concerns around distraction, “infoxication” (‘intoxication of information’) and technological overuse—challenges that require teacher mediation and support. Dutch teachers likewise contest the assumption that students are inherently digitally adept; they observe practical difficulties with basic information management (e.g., retrieving documents from learning platforms) and emphasize that social media fluency does not equate to meaningful digital literacy. In both studies, teachers call for explicit instruction in evaluative skills (e.g., identifying reliable sources, interpreting feedback) alongside targeted teacher professional development to scaffold responsible, goal-aligned use of tools.
- Over-reliance on automation. Both groups express unease about the opacity introduced by automated aids (e.g., translation tools, AI writing support). Spanish teachers frame this unease primarily as a deficit in critical thinking and a broader risk environment (i.e., distractions, abuse of technology), while Dutch teachers explicitly link automation to threats to learners' agency and self-perception: when students outsource language production to tools, it becomes difficult to gauge their underlying competence, and learners may undervalue their own emerging resources.

Key differences

Similarly, three key differences between both contexts have also been found, namely:

- Prominence of resource constraints and their implications for device policy. A major difference lies in the prominence of infrastructural limitations and smartphone policy. In the Spanish study, “lack of resources” is reported by all participants. Relatedly, a distinct theme centres on prohibiting smartphones in class, reflecting a risk-mitigation stance grounded in distraction and classroom management concerns. By contrast, the Dutch account foregrounds pedagogical countermeasures (e.g., paper-based tasks, monitored in-class production).
- Plurilingual identity and its (non-)integration into digital pedagogy. Only the Dutch teachers thematize learners' plurilingual identities as an acknowledged asset that remains largely untapped within technology-supported pedagogy. Teachers recognize multilingual

backgrounds positively in interpersonal ways but hesitate to embed plurilingual strategies into systematic, tech-mediated designs. The Spanish study, while it addresses informal and non-formal learning practices and perceived student competence, does not thematically foreground plurilingual identity as a design opportunity within digital environments.

- Informal and non-formal learning. The Spanish study explicitly connects technological advantages to students' informal and non-formal learning, suggesting that accessibility and adaptability extend practice beyond formal classrooms. This theme is not explicitly developed in the Dutch account, which concentrates on classroom authenticity, monitoring, and shifts toward paper-based, face-to-face tasks to counterbalance digital dependency. The divergence may reflect different focal concerns: Spanish teachers view technology as a bridge to additional learning contexts, while Dutch teachers focus on guarding the integrity of formal assessment and in-class production.

Conclusions

These findings offer a general view of how secondary education students and teachers in five countries (Aruba, Belgium, Spain, Sweden, and the Netherlands) perceive and engage with technology in relation to language learning and linguistic identity development, with a deeper view in Spain and the Netherlands considering also the qualitative approach using interviews and focus groups.

Regarding the quantitative data, the findings show that digital device use for school-related tasks is widespread, though patterns vary substantially across countries. While students in Sweden and Spain most frequently use devices daily or multiple times per day, those in Belgium and the Netherlands report more weekly use. Aruba presents an intermediate but relatively intensive pattern. Most students are also regularly required to complete assignments on a computer outside school, with notable cross-country differences in how often teachers request such tasks.

Moreover, students' attitudes toward technology-supported multilingual learning are generally positive across contexts, with Spain reporting the highest mean scores and Sweden and the Netherlands somewhat lower, though still positive. In contrast, multilingual digital practices—actual use of languages other than the home language in digital environments—display a different distribution: Aruba and Sweden show the highest behavioural engagement, whereas Spain reports the lowest. This discrepancy indicates an attitude–behaviour gap in the Spanish context: although Spanish students value technology as a resource for multilingual learning, this is not reflected in their everyday multilingual digital behaviour, likely due to the strong online presence of Spanish. Within Spain, plurilingual students demonstrate significantly higher levels of multilingual digital practices compared to bilingual and monolingual peers, highlighting the influence of linguistic profiles on digital language use.

In the case of teachers, quantitative results show that secondary teachers across the five participating countries report a broadly consistent pattern of assigning computer-based homework. Only a small minority (approximately 3%) never require students to complete assignments digitally outside school. Most teachers integrate such tasks regularly: nearly 30% assign them weekly, around 24% daily, and approximately 8–9% multiple times per day or during specific project periods. Occasional use is also common, with about 17–18% assigning computer-based homework monthly or a few times per year. A chi-square test indicated no

statistically significant cross-country differences, suggesting that the overall frequency of digital homework assignments is relatively uniform across contexts.

Teachers' digital literacy self-efficacy is generally high. A four-item scale assessing confidence in technological problem-solving, skill acquisition, technological awareness, and technology use demonstrated strong internal consistency and a clear one-factor structure. The mean score (3.83 on a 5-point scale) indicates that teachers typically perceive themselves as competent digital users, with responses clustering in the "often" to "very often" range. Very few teachers rate their digital literacy at low levels, implying widespread confidence in managing and adopting digital tools. Taken together, these results highlight a teaching workforce that both regularly incorporates digital homework tasks and feels well-equipped to navigate contemporary technological demands.

Regarding the qualitative part of the study, focusing on more detailed students' and teachers' perspectives on the use of technology (both inside and outside the classroom) for language-related activities in two distinct European contexts, Spain and the Netherlands, several similarities can be found. In the case of students, participants from both countries consider that technology is a convenient and efficient tool for immediate needs, although they have limited trust in translation and AI tools and they prefer human mediation and social interaction for language use and learning. Moreover, both groups recognise the relevance of out-of-class learning through media exposure.

Teachers from both countries also show similarities in their responses, as they converge in seeing technology as motivating and access-enhancing, although it is necessary to be cautious. Both Spanish and Dutch teachers highlight the importance of digital literacy, and demystify the idea of "digital natives," as both groups observe practical difficulties with basic information management. In this line, both groups convey discomfort regarding the lack of transparency that automated tools (translation tools, AI tools) introduce.

It must be noted that there are also divergences depending on the context. Overall, the comparison reveals four notable divergences in how Spanish and Dutch students conceptualise technology-supported learning. First, Dutch students show a more metacognitive understanding of competence, distinguishing procedural task completion from authentic communicative ability, whereas Spanish students focus mainly on behavioural risks such as dependency or reduced effort. Second, social interaction emerges as a stronger motivational force for Dutch students,

who link technology use to multilingual family networks and real-life communication, while Spanish students emphasise interpersonal interaction more generally. Finally, Dutch students report purposeful plurilingual practices to aid learning, whereas Spanish students do not foreground other languages as strategic resources, making such practices less visible in their accounts.

Moreover, the comparison highlights three key differences shaping how Spanish and Dutch teachers approach educational technology. First, resource constraints are central in Spain: Spanish teachers consistently cite infrastructural shortages and smartphone bans, whereas Dutch teachers focus on pedagogical solutions rather than device restrictions. Second, Spanish teachers link technology to informal and non-formal learning beyond the classroom, while Dutch teachers prioritise safeguarding classroom authenticity. These contrasts indicate differing priorities: structural feasibility in Spain and pedagogical refinement in the Netherlands.

The interplay between student practices, teacher beliefs, and institutional support mirrors the dynamic connections within the Pluridentities framework (Pluridentities, 2025), particularly the need for better alignment between technology, language policy, and the learning environment to fully leverage students' linguistic capital.

However, an important limitation of this working paper is that the findings rely exclusively on self-reported attitudes and practices. Moreover, it is also worth to mention that the Dutch qualitative data is based on first readings of 6 transcripts out of 21. Such data, while valuable for capturing participants' perceptions, are inherently constrained by factors such as social desirability bias, selective recall, and discrepancies between stated beliefs and actual behaviour. As a result, the extent to which these self-reports accurately represent students' and teachers' everyday digital engagement within the classroom remains uncertain. Future research employing observational or ethnographic methods would therefore be essential for providing a more fine-grained and empirically grounded understanding of classroom dynamics, interactional patterns, and the authentic use of digital tools in pedagogical contexts. These methods could help identify behavioural nuances that self-report measures may overlook, offering a more robust basis for interpreting how technology is integrated into learning processes.

Despite this, the implications of this research point to several key steps. On the one hand, educational policies should encourage the active use of multiple languages in digital contexts,

moving beyond passive exposure to promote meaningful communication and creative expression. On the other, teachers and curriculum designers should integrate digital tools in ways that reflect students' preferences and habits, making language learning more engaging and relevant..

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